

ESTIMATION OF BIOFILM ACTIVITIES ON BIOFILTER CARRIERS FROM RECIRCULATING AQUACULTURE SYSTEM BY RESPIROMETRY

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Introduction

Biofilm, the aggregates of microbial layers that are attached on the surface of biofilter carriers, plays a central role in nutrients removal in recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) to achieve high degree water reuse for fish production (Chen et al., 2006). The bacterial activities in biofilm are of great importance for surveillance and management of RAS biofilter, but cannot easily be measured. Moreover, a biofilm detachment process and laboratory equipment are required for current methods to characterize the biofilm, which seem unsuitable for on-site application in a RAS facility. The present study was conducted with an aim to develop a simple and reproducible method that allows *ex-situ* estimation of biofilm activities without destroying biofilm integrity.

Materials and methods

Three different types of biocarriers, extruded polypropylene (EPP), injection molded polypropylene (IMPP) and polymeric foam (PF) from biofilters connected to the same RAS were tested in our tailor-made respirometry system. The oxygen consumption rates of biofilm in respirometric chambers packed with biocarriers were measured after intermittent spiking with either ammonium, nitrite or acetate. The standard substrate degradation batch kinetics tests for evaluating biofilter performance were also conducted to confirm the feasibility of our proposed method as a means to assessing biofilter performance.

Results

Results showed that the method allowed estimation of endogenous respiration rates, as well as respiration of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB), nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB) and heterotrophic bacteria (HB) in biofilm. The highest activities, calculated and standardized as volumetric oxygen consumption rate (VOCR), were found in PF with values of 764, 677 and 166 g O₂·m⁻³·d⁻¹ for AOB, NOB and HB, respectively (**Figure 1**). Furthermore, substrate degradation batch tests matched respirometric tests well for all three tested carriers to evaluate biofilter performance (**Figure 2**).

Discussion and conclusion

The higher activities of AOB, NOB and HB in biofilm of PF carriers suggest that PF carriers could achieve more effective removal of ammonia, nitrite and organic matter in RAS water treatment. This is in support of findings from Shitu et al., (2020) that found PF carriers achieved higher nitrification performance than plastic media in MBBR treating RAS wastewater. The deviation between the predicted and observed values for biofilter performance for PF carriers may be the result of different factors, such as that i) respirometric tests and nitrification batch kinetic tests were performed separately, ii) differences in hydraulic conditions in reactors (closed respirometric chamber vs. open beaker) might have an influence on oxygen and substrate diffusion, iii) a part of ammonia, as well as small amount of electrons from TAN oxidation and nitrite oxidation processes are used for cell synthesis, which has a lower oxygen demand than predicted by the theoretical oxygen demand (Liu and Wang, 2012). In conclusion, the proposed method allows estimating activities of biofilm attached on biofilter carriers from a

freshwater RAS by measuring oxygen consumption rates following substrate spikes. The designed intermittent respirometer platform achieved replicated and non-invasive oxygen measurement without disturbing biofilm integrity. This method allowed complete estimation of metabolic activity of endogenous respiration, NOB, AOB and HB in biofilm within less than five hours. Comparison study with standard substrate degradation kinetic batch tests for assessing biological processes in biofilter confirmed the feasibility of our proposed method to evaluate the biofilter performance. Our study provides a potential tool of monitoring and diagnosis for RAS biofilter and a better understanding of biofilm on the carriers, which would benefit biofilter design and water quality management in RAS.

Figure 1. Volumetric oxygen consumption rates (VOCR, g O₂·m⁻³·d⁻¹) measured in three different types of carriers. Endogenous VOCR was measured in water without substrates, ammonium (AOB+NOB) and nitrite oxidation (NOB) related VOCR in presence of TAN or nitrite, respectively and heterotrophic activity (HB) during addition of acetate. EPP=Extruded polypropylene, IMPP=Injection molded polypropylene, PF=Polymeric foam. Bars and error bars denote mean ± standard deviation of the mean (n=3; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001; ns=not significant).

Figure 2. Biofilter performance assessment comparison between predicted values based on VOCR (volumetric oxygen consumption rate) data from respirometric tests and observed values from substrate degradation batch kinetic tests for three tested carriers (EPP=Extruded polypropylene, IMPP=Injection molded polypropylene, PF=Polymeric foam). VTR, VNR and VAR were volumetric TAN, nitrite and acetate removal rate representing as parameters for evaluating biofilter performance.

References

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